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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V.0	03/01/2024	First draft
V.1	12/03/2024	Final version

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
 SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Abbreviations and definitions

The abbreviations and definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [\[ref\]](#).

1 Introduction

In line with the Description of the Action and to support dissemination to the interested public, audio-visual material has been produced for AIDAVA. The material is designed to effectively communicate the project's goals and significance to a wide-ranging audience. This includes the general public, the scientific community, and various related projects and initiatives. Our aim is to increase awareness and understanding of AIDAVA's objectives and the positive effects it aims to achieve.

2 Description of Activities

2.1 Purpose

The AIDAVA project film is designed to enhance public awareness and understanding of the project's objectives in a format that is both engaging and easy to comprehend. The aim is to showcase the project goals in a way that is both informative and entertaining, while also highlighting the potential impact of the project's outcomes on European society.

The movie clip explains the background of the project's objectives, i.e. using easy-to-digest language, the short clip aims to highlight AIDAVA's approach to developing a trustworthy AI-powered virtual assistant, which uses artificial intelligence technologies to clean and harmonise heterogeneous health data from diverse sources, delivering personal health records that benefit both patients and healthcare professionals. The video strives to present the project's vision, mission, and approach in an appealing and cheerful manner.

Furthermore, the film is providing information about the project's progress and the funding provided by the European Commission, ensuring that this aspect of the project is widely understood and appreciated.

Target audience

The AIDAVA film is mainly intended for the general public, but it will also help disseminate the project to the scientific community and political stakeholders. It has been designed and produced to be used in online communications as well as events and meetings if appropriate. It can be used by AIDAVA project partners and the European Commission for dissemination purposes.

Concept and Production

To increase the public visibility of AIDAVA and to communicate AIDAVA's aims, objectives and expected outcomes, an animated short clip was produced within the first year and a half of the project.

The clip has a length of ~2 minutes and features motion design of elements and typography in a symbolic realistic animation style. In a simplified manner the film vividly illustrates the key aspects of AIDAVA, making it accessible to a broader public.

After describing the current problematic and the frustrating challenge of managing and sharing personal health information, the clip addresses the objectives of AIDAVA. The project aim is to simplify this complex process by developing an AI-powered virtual assistant capable of harmonizing and integrating diverse health data. This assistant streamlines data cleaning, offering a centralized platform for individuals to manage their health records effortlessly. Additionally, it facilitates seamless data sharing with healthcare providers and researchers through a user-friendly app. The clip finds easily accessible symbols and metaphors to illustrate AIDAVA's innovative approach.

Patient support and involvement have been fundamental to AIDAVA's mission. To ensure that the clip resonates with patients and the general public, the concept and script were shared with patient consultants via AIDAVA patient organizations (ECPC and EHN) actively engaged in the project. Their invaluable feedback not only influenced the duration of the video and its visualization of metaphorical processes but also guided the choice of wording to make the project more relatable to a broader

audience. This collaborative approach helped embed patient perspectives into the final version of the film.

Figure 1. AIDAVA Audio-Visual Material: Conceptualization and Production Workflow

As the leader of task 6.1 (Project Communication), P3-EURICE has managed the complete production process, starting with the creation of the film concept and voice over text and animation conception **with the support of the AIDAVA Communication Committee members.** Production steps like recording and animations were contracted to a professional service provider with several rounds of revisions based on feed-back provided by P3-EURICE and partners involved in this task. Especially in the early stages of the concept phase, the consortium has been heavily involved to ensure the highest possible identification with the film.

The whole production of the movie started in mid-June 2023, and the film was released in November 2023. The film was produced for online distribution as the most cost-effective means of dissemination.

3 Results

The film has been published on the AIDAVA website on 30 November 2023. All consortium partners were encouraged to make use of their websites and news channels or existing social media channels (X, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube etc.) to increase the project's visibility.

On the occasion of the film release, AIDAVA partners were provided with a guidance document containing communication recommendations (please see Annex I) and a template of a news release (please see Annex II), allowing individual adaption and convenient press distribution.

As the AIDAVA film has been designed and produced to be used in online communication, the key communication channels were defined as follows:

Websites / News sections

- AIDAVA website - [Home | AIDAVA](#)
- Websites / news sections of partner institutions involved in AIDAVA (e.g. Eurice: www.eurice.eu)

Youtube / Other video sharing channels

- Video-sharing channels of partner institutions involved in AIDAVA (e.g. EURICE: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oRLB7iBDYnw>)

Additionally, links to the video were posted at:

- AIDAVA LinkedIn profile [AIDAVA: Company Page Admin | LinkedIn](#)
- AIDAVA X feed (@aidava_project as well as other social networking sites of partner institutions (or participants)
- LinkedIn profiles (or other business networking sites) of partners

Events

- Scientific conferences and meetings, events and activities

Figure 2: Screenshot of website

Figure 3: Screenshot of a LinkedIn post

Figure 4: Screenshot of a “X” post

Figure 5: Video on Youtube

4 Deviations

Because the AIDAVA Communication Committee had been involved in the first rounds of the creation of the concept of the animated movie, the feedback loops had been longer than originally anticipated. This resulted in a later release date of the film than announced in the DoA (where it had been scheduled for M12). This delay had been communicated to and was been approved by the EC officer.

5 Conclusions

The AIDAVA project has produced a 1:49 min film, which introduces the main aims of the project and explains the innovative aspect of AIDAVA.

The film has been designed and produced to be used by AIDAVA project partners and the European Commission in online communications or in events and meetings. Its dissemination will help to raise awareness for and inform on the scientific content and outputs of the project, and about the need for and existence of European research initiatives.

6 Annexe I Briefing Document

AIDAVA - AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

Promotion of the AIDAVA Animated Clip

As part of the AIDAVA communication and dissemination activities, we have produced an **animated clip**. The video targets a broad audience of interested lay people, various players involved in data science and artificial intelligence as well as policymakers, the scientific community and members of academia.

Using easy-to-digest language, the short clip aims to highlight AIDAVA's approach to developing a trustworthy AI-powered virtual assistant, which uses artificial intelligence technologies to clean and harmonise heterogeneous health data from diverse sources, delivering personal health records that benefit both patients and healthcare professionals. The video strives to present the project's vision, mission, approach in an appealing and cheerful manner.

We invite you to promote the clip via any of your communication channels, such as:

- ✓ Your institution's or personal websites;
- ✓ Your institution's or your personal social media and video channels, including Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, etc.;
- ✓ Any suitable conferences, workshops, trade fairs, training events, open days, exhibitions, etc.

If you wish to directly embed the clip on your institutional website, the file is available for download on the management platform with subtitle in English burned and a version without subtitles and a subtitle file (.srt) can also be found on the management platform (https://aidava.eurice.eu/projects/documents/dmsf?folder_id=53). Moreover, the film can be accessed via the AIDAVA website and is made available on YouTube (<https://youtu.be/oRLB7iBDYnw>).

To minimise your efforts, we have prepared a news release and a social media post which you are welcome to use or adapt according to your needs. We have also collated and attached a couple of screenshots you may use for illustration.

Please kindly let us know once you have published the news so we can keep track of the promotion activities for our next report. Thank you!

Social Media Post (suggestion) X

How to enable efficient curation and publishing of #personalhealthdata, delivering #reusable #personalhealthrecords for the benefit of #patients and #researchers? Check out the brand-new #AIDAVA video below to learn about our vision!

<https://youtu.be/oRLB7iBDYnw>

@EU_HaDEA

Social Media Post (suggestion) LinkedIn

How to enable efficient curation and publishing of #personalhealthdata, delivering #reusable #personalhealthrecords for the benefit of #patients and #researchers?

Integrated, high-quality personal health data (#PHD) represents a potential wealth of knowledge for healthcare systems, but there is no reliable conduit for this data to become interoperable, AI-ready and reuse-ready at scale across institutions at the national and #EU levels.

Learn about the innovative #AIDAVA approach to democratise participation in data curation & publishing by citizens/patients leading to overall savings in health care costs (through disease prevention, early diagnosis, personalized medicine) and supporting delivery of the European Health Data Space.

Check out the brand-new #AIDAVA video below to learn about our vision!

@EU_HaDEA #HorizonEU #AI #DataScience #HealthData

[Add video or include the YouTube link!]

News Release (suggestion)

An AI powered virtual assistant delivering personal health data records that benefits patients and healthcare professionals: AIDAVA Project Launches Animated Video

Integrated, high-quality personal health data (PHD) represents a potential wealth of knowledge for healthcare systems, but there is no reliable conduit for this data to become interoperable, AI-ready and reuse-ready at scale across institutions at the national and EU levels.

Learn about the innovative AIDAVA approach to democratise participation in data curation & publishing by citizens/patients leading to overall savings in health care costs (through disease prevention, early diagnosis, personalized medicine) and supporting delivery of the European Health Data Space.

The clip is available on the AIDAVA project website <https://aidava.eu/> and on YouTube <https://youtu.be/oRLB7iBDYnw>.

About AIDAVA

All available personal health data of an individual in one consistent semantic model: AIDAVA is developing a digital solution, orchestrating diverse artificial intelligence technologies, for more efficient curation and publishing of personal health data, delivering interoperable and reusable personal health records for the benefit of patients and clinical researchers.

The AIDAVA consortium consists of twelve partners and two associate partners from nine European countries who have set out to achieve a quantum leap in automating the curation and publication of personal health data by orchestrating multiple Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based solutions.

For more information on the project, please visit <https://aidava.eu/>